

SPEAKING ENGLISH IS A FRIGHT IN PAKISTANI STUDENTS: REASONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Dr. Sidra Ahmad
sidra.ahmad@ue.edu.pk

PhD Applied Linguistics, Department of English Language and Literature, University of Education, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

Iqra Iqbal
iqra.iqbal@ue.edu.pk

MPhil Literature, Department of English Language and Literature, University of Education, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan.

Asad Hussain
asadh0132@gmail.com

MPhil Scholar in Applied Linguistics, Department of Applied Linguistics, Government College University, Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan.

Abstract

The study attempts to highlight the difficulties of Pakistani students in speaking English Language and contributes to providing remedies for these problems. English language learners in Pakistan, no matter how much they know about it, still face certain difficulties in its Speaking skill. For collecting data, a scripted interview was conducted among the random undergraduate students at the Business Administration Department, Fine Arts Department and English Department of the University of Education, Lahore to unveil the English language speaking difficulties. After knowing the difficulties, researchers planned some activities for the selected sample and practiced these activities in classrooms. This engineered treatment was given for 8 weeks to students and again the scripted interview was taken to enlighten the before and after effects. The research introduces the recommendations in form of activities which are helpful for teachers who teach English as a major or minor subject to different disciplines. The purpose of basic education is to make the learner gain necessary skills for improving communication skills through which s/he can perform better in every field of life. The study facilitates the students to know about their spoken problems first and then to engage themselves in activities to overcome them; moreover, teachers will also be benefited by applying the given activities to make their students eloquent speakers of English Language.

Keywords: *English Speaking, English Teachers, Difficulties, Activities, Suggestions*

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sidra Ahmad (PhD Applied Linguistics, Department of English Language and Literature, University of Education, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan). **Email:** sidra.ahmad@ue.edu.pk

1. Introduction

The present research investigates that how important spoken skills are for undergraduate students. The research also figures out the causes of poor speaking skills of students and introduces the solution to these problems in form of activities. The present study helps to understand the problem of poor English speaking of undergraduate students. It provides the teachers a signpost to follow for making them eloquent speakers of English. In addition, learners will also know about the areas they need to improve to develop better spoken abilities. Amongst the four basic learning skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing) speaking ability is the most important. Obviously, it is necessary to develop communication skills. English oral communication skills are part of this skill set, for this reason, students should be supported to gain these skills. Learners of English in Pakistan do not have opportunities to speak English outside the classrooms, and for many of them, the course book is the only place where they meet English; majority of them belong to middle or lower middle class where they do not have chance to excel the said skill. Communication skill has the status to exercise the power and to persuade the audience. In today's world where English is the official language of many countries of world so it is rightly significant that communication of an individuals be highly refined. The results of this study can help the Ministry of Education, the teachers, the curriculum designers, and learners who find difficult to speak in English, and consequently.

2. Literature Review

As far as importance of speaking skills is concerned, , Ur (1996) considered speaking as the most important skill among four skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing) because people who know a language are referred to as speakers of that language. This argues that if you claim to speak two or more than two language it indicates that you can proficiently use it in speaking as well writing. According to Ur (1996), there are many factors that cause difficulty in speaking, and they are as follows:

1. Inhibition. Students are worried about making mistakes, fearful of criticism, or simply shy.
2. Nothing to say. Students have no motive to express themselves.
3. Low or uneven participation. Only one participant can talk at a time because of large classes and the tendency of some learners to dominate, while others speak very little or not at all.
4. Mother-tongue use. Learners who share the same mother tongue tend to use it because it is easier and because learners feel less exposed if they are speaking their mother tongue.

Speaking skill enables the learners to better convey their thoughts and sentiments. The use of English as a second language (ESL) or foreign language (EFL) in oral communication is, without a doubt, one of the most common but highly complex activities necessary to be considered when teaching the English language especially because we —live at a time where the ability to speak English fluently has become a must, especially who want to advance in certain fields of human endeavor (Al-Sibai, 2004, p.3). Tanveer (2007) suggests that the most common cause of poor speaking skills in undergraduate students was found to be anxiety.

Heriansyah (2012) discusses the difficulties and causes perceived by English department students of Syiah Kuala University in learning speaking. This study reveals that all students encountered various difficulties in English speaking ‘lack of vocabulary’, while ‘being afraid of making mistakes’ was the prime cause of problem which hindered them to speak. The researcher finds many solutions in this study as speaking skills do not stand alone but they are supported by the mastery of vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation and meanwhile, the lecturers of these subjects need to increase student’s mastery.

According Hosni (2014) speaking is the active use of language to express meaning, and for young learners, the spoken language is the medium through which a new language is encountered, understood, practiced, and learnt. This study revealed that the main speaking difficulties encountered by grade 5 students are linguistic difficulties, mother tongue use, and inhibition. Students are unable to speak in English because they lack the necessary vocabulary items and grammar structures. They also lack sentence formation skills, which result in using the mother tongue. Students also think of making mistakes in speaking in front of their classmates very embarrassing, which results in preferring not to speak to avoid such situations.

Hussain (2017) investigates three parameters of spoken skills of the students i.e., the importance of speaking skills, the types of mistakes made in English speaking, the causes of poor speaking skills and the solution to the problems in speaking of undergraduate students. The researcher suggests that to increase the student’s participation in the class the teachers should encourage the students through a friendly gesture and class environment moreover they should have confidence to make mistakes in order to acquire communication skills. Teachers should try to get information about the students past academic experience and to help them accordingly to overcome their difficulties.

Burns (2017) reviews the theory and practice of recent approaches to the teaching of speaking. The study argues that teachers need to have awareness of a range of such theoretical areas in order to understand and address the speaking needs of their students

explicitly. Through a survey some key areas of research are introduced by researcher that could enhance pedagogical knowledge and it is concluded by considering further directions in research on the teaching of speaking via new technology which offers great potential for wide-ranging developments in the teaching of spoken language.

Susilawati (2017) attempts to find out the most dominant and least problem faced by students in their presentation. The finding showed that the most dominant problem faced by the students in doing the presentation is vocabulary and the least problem in doing the presentation is fear of making mistake. The researcher gives some suggestions as: it would be better if they make speaking English as a habit to develop their ability in using English as a means of communication rather than a subject in which their struggling. Since they are foreign language learners, they should gained awareness that speaking English is very essential, and in demanded to speak fluently and accurately toward the target language they should realize that the problems they face today might be faced by other students too.

Present study enlightens the factor that development of speaking skills among students on undergraduate level has become most important. Without good speaking skills it is not possible to have command over a language, thus the development of speaking skills is the most important.

3.Methodology

Present study involves 60 students of BFA, Business Administration and English department of University of Education, Lahore to extract the data. 20 students of each department have been involved to conduct an interview. Via this structured interview, the responses of participants have been locked regarding their difficulties in speaking English. The designed activities have been practiced in classroom for eliminating their horrified feeling about English and making them well-expressed speakers of this language. After keeping them under observation of 8 weeks, another interview has been held to know the reaction and improvement of students. The results have been finalized with the help of feedback given by participants before and after treatment of activities.

4.Findings and Discussion

4.1. Responses of interview

Below presented interview was conducted before starting the research and the responses of participants have been given in percentage.

Table 1

Sr.#	Questions	Responses
1	Do you want to speak English?	98%
2	Are you able to communicate your idea in English in any situation?	9%
3	Do you face any difficulty while speaking English?	95%
4	Which problem do you face?	See table 2
5	Are you willing to be a good English speaker?	98%
6	Did you ever attend any course/class to improve you spoken?	91%
7	Do you need any assistance/help/guideline for making you good speaker?	95%
8	Will you like to be helped in your class?	80%
9	Will you like to participate in activities with your fellows?	78%
10	Have you ever been involved in such activities?	95%

The results show that students want to be a good speaker of English language and they share their feelings regarding this issue. The results communicate that being an undergraduate student they do not know how to get grip on spoken or how to express their ideas in English. The answers of questions lead the study towards its purpose that students genuinely face problems and here should be some remedies to overcome them. Most strikingly, the response of question number 4 set the track for this research that is shown in following mentioning the major difficulties addressed by the students.

4.2. Problems of learners

Interview brought many big problems on the surface which were being faced by the learners. The result has been presented in tabular form; for making them more self-explanatory percentage of problem has also be given with replies.

Table 2

Sr.#	Problems	Replies	%age
1	Lack of confidence	31	51
2	Fear of mistake	24	40
3	Lack of vocabulary	12	20
4	Fear of insult	10	16
5	Pressure of good performance	7	11
6	Solo performance	6	10
7	Pronunciation problem	4	6
8	Tense consciousness	3	5
9	Poor Accent	3	5

Above shown table has been set according to the degree of difficulty which students face while speaking. Results present a very clear picture that ‘lack of confidence’ is a huge problem of students. They said that cannot speak in front of audience because they know they will commit mistakes. ‘Fear of mistakes’ is on second number in table. It shows that learners are conscious about their performance that they want to speak error freely. For being a good speaker student also know that they are required to have enough vocabulary meanwhile they face the problem of ‘lack of vocabulary’. Participants were asked that if any script be given them to memorize and speak will they be able to speak accurately; majority replied less confidently. This state also indicates that even having the content to speak they have problem of lack of confidence.

Above mentioned table represents that ‘lack of vocabulary’ is also a faced by students. This has been analyzed that learners know much about the language and specifically the content they want to convey but they themselves decide that do not know. Many of the subjects denied to speak and refused to take part in solo activity but once they were triggered, they performed very well; even they acknowledged that they can speak and they knew the content already. Research unveils that ‘fear of insult’ is likewise a problem of many students because of this they do not dare to speak. During research it has been observed that learners seemed very much conscious before starting any activity about their performance but they were treated in such a way that they succeeded to overcome the said problem. ‘Pressure of good performance’ and ‘Solo performance’ are much closed. The reason behind this factor is that students do not want to perform individually. During research it has been examined that they predicted they cannot speak well; this is why, they were not ready to act solely and take the feedback in front of others. Here was another factor involved that many learners had faced such environment where they were laughed at or discouraged for making mistakes.

Table presents that ‘tense consciousness’ and ‘poor accent’ are with same scores. This problem was highlighted by a few students. The research explores that students who were suffering from these problems they were not with accurate knowledge about their difficulties. When they were asked about the other problems then they replied that they face ‘lack of confidence’ and ‘vocabulary issue’ as well. It has also been observed that students wants to speak in native English style so that they also demand form teacher to work on accent.

These were the problems highlighted by the students via interview. The following section presents the solutions to overcome these problems.

4.3. Solution through activities

After knowing the problems, the researchers designed some activities for each problem. These activities were conducted in classroom with selected samples to resolute the problems. The activities are given below in front of their relevant problem for which they were conducted.

Table 3

Activities	For which problem?
Catch your partner	Fear of mistake
Know about your colleague	Fear of insult
Set your priority	Lack of confidence
Listen your voice on mobile	Accent problem
Word bank	Pronunciation problem
Elevator Talk	Pressure of good performance
Spot the difference	Tense consciousness
Role play	Solo performance
Your response	Lack of vocabulary

4.4. Description of Activities

The description of above-mentioned activities has been given in appendix. They have been elaborated in steps along with the procedure which presents the way that how to conduct them. First activity was planned for the problem of 'Fear of mistake' and it was noticed that they were not found confident while speaking in front of audience. During this activity, students had been found speaking loudly due to which for a short period of time they forgot their fear and seen busy to catch their partners. Moreover, this activity only required the name of the partner so students repeated the content many times for the completion of the activity. This repetition gave them confidence that they can speak in front of other people.

Second activity was conducted for 'Fear of insult'. This activity enhanced the courage of participants to take part in it. It was observed that students were anxious to know about each other due to which their fear disappeared to be insulted in front of others. This activity also helped the participants in both ways as: firstly, participants were telling to each other about themselves and meanwhile they were jotting down the points to

introduce the co-participant. Secondly, this activity was conducted in peers so that the fear of insult was not that much noticeable as it was before starting it.

Third fear was 'Lack of confidence'. The researchers engaged the students in activity in such an enthusiastic way that they were found to suppress their laggard performance and very quickly they seemed self-reliant. This activity proved beneficial in multiple perspectives like: participants firstly performed individually and formed their own logics for task, then, they mingled with their co-partner and presented their views, finally, they worked in groups and endeavored to convince other groups. During this task, it was noted that students were more interested to present their ideas and persuade others rather than the pressure of fear.

'Accent problem' was one of the spoken difficulties and due to its percentage, it was put on fourth number. The designed activity for this problem was done on frequent bases. The purpose was to bring a noticeable change in students' accent. It was seen that students played a very energetic role in this activity and they were concerned to make their accents better. Moreover, due to this activity, students were found to try speak in English confidently. They also admitted this factor that since they are trying to improve their accents it is giving them self-assurance to contribute in communication in different contexts.

After accent problem, this research shows next striking feature of spoken difficulty in form of 'Pronunciation problem'. Before conducting this activity, it was experienced that students claimed about their pronunciation problem for difficult words only rather they were pronouncing some very easy words in wrong way. This task proved influential equally-for pronunciation purpose and for vocabulary building- because participants were supposed to utter the word accurately and tell its denotative meaning as well. It was also fruitful in this way that students were having a handsome collection of words to use in daily routine.

The research highlights another problem that is 'Pressure of good performance'; to eliminate this issue activity named 'elevator talk' has been designed. Participants were recorded proactive during this activity as they were not attentive towards performance rather their purpose was to convey the idea to other team members. The reason behind this problem was noticed that participant (with this issue) has difficulty because of presence of some good speakers around her: due to this factor they do not try to speak. But with the help of designed activity this fear disappeared somehow and students realized that to communicate a good idea can help to be a good speaker.

The study points out 'Tense consciousness' as a problem in speaking English. This problem was controlled by an insightful activity entitled 'spot the difference'. Less

practice of speaking in different contexts was noticed as a prominent aspect to be conscious about tense. Participants were very fond of to do said activity and they took part very energetically. Their response was observed which helped to overcome the difficulty. Throughout this task, they were trying different words/phrases/tenses to convey their collected information as compare to be worried about sentence structure.

‘Solo performance’ has also been found as a difficulty in this study. Although, very few responses were recorded for this issue but researchers felt a need to suppress this problem. ‘Role play’ was selected to subdue the fear of solo performance. Participants enjoyed this activity and performed confidently. With the help of this activity, researchers attained their objective (to make the learner a good speaker) very smartly. As on one hand, participant was taking part in this activity having the feeling to perform in group and on other hand, she was delivering the dialogues individually. By this step, the participant was felt self-reliant while speaking English.

Lastly, the research notices ‘Lack of vocabulary’ as a hindrance in speaking English. The activity titled ‘Your response’ was conducted to overcome this problem. An interesting factor has been seen in this duration that students claimed about this problem but actually many of them were not confident to speak even having content in written with them. This activity assisted them to speak using multipurpose phraseology and have self-assurance to communicate their thoughts without any fear in mind.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research findings and discussions, it can be concluded that the cause of problems in speaking English is that most students were ‘being afraid of making errors. There are two kinds of problems found in the students while speaking English: one is linguistic problems and other is non-linguistic problems. The study shows that teachers do not spend enough time for speaking that is because of the shortage of time because in curriculum and syllabi priority is given to the coverage of the textbook topics, in which more emphasis is put on teaching reading and writing rather than speaking. The research also enlightens the indispensable need of generating and practicing the ‘spoken activities’ in real classroom context so that teacher could know the learners’ problems regarding speaking and cure them timely.

5.1. Recommendations

5.1.1. On teacher’s behalf

1. The instructor should have knowledge about the needs of her/his learners so that the activities be designed according to the level of learners.
2. Teacher should make students learn in friendly environment without making them conscious about their performance at early stage. Once they get indulged in the activities and start to take part actively then they should be told about their act.
3. Above introduced all activities should be conducted in class on regular basis even once or twice a week to make the learners eager for learning.
4. Teacher should welcome the mistakes of students for enhancing their confidence.
5. Teachers need to be trained on how to integrate speaking to other skills and how to teach it communicatively.

5.1.2. On learner's behalf

1. Students themselves should know accurately about their problem/s. If s/he would have complete knowledge about her/his shortcoming then s/he will be treated properly and effectively.
2. They should cooperate with instructor to overcome their problems and follow the instruction given for conducting activities. Because poor attention can cause poor learning.
3. Practice is an essential part for better results so that students should do practice except the set timings for activities in class.
4. They should be the part of such forums where they could have chance to listen and speak in English: because of this exercise they would have experience to interact with different people.

5.1.3. On administration's behalf

1. Administration should do some arrangements (seminar, workshop, and training) in institutions where teachers should be given special training on how to handle the poor speaking skills of students.
2. Here should be enough time to work on spoken abilities through class activities and resources should be provided to teachers.
3. English supervisors, school administrators, and staff of the Ministry of Education should work together for making the students good speakers.
4. Course designers and curriculum developers should work cooperatively in order to reach a productive result between what is introduced in the textbooks and how it should be taught and assessed.

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Appendix- A

English speaking difficulties

(Before)

1. Do you want to speak English?
.....
2. Are you able to communicate your idea in English in any situation?
.....
3. Do you face any difficulty while speaking English?
.....
4. Which problem do you face?
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
5. Are you willing to be a good English speaker?
.....
6. Did you ever attend any course/class to improve you spoken?
.....
7. Do you need any assistance/help/guideline for making you good speaker?
.....
8. Will you like to be helped in your class?
.....
9. Will you like to participate in activities with your fellows?
.....
10. Have you ever been involved in such activities?
.....

Appendix-B

English speaking difficulties

(After)

1. Did you improve as compare to your previous situation?

2. Which thing you enjoyed during this treatment?
3. Was this treatment beneficial for you?
4. Would you like to be treated by such activities in future for improving other language skills?
5. Do you think that such activities should be taught by subject teacher or any other?
6. Was teacher's contribution impactful during this treatment?
7. Which tasks you enjoyed; individual, peer or group?
8. Do you think that collaboration helps to learn more effectively and quickly?

Appendix-C

Activity 1

Know about your colleague

Students will be divided into groups consisting of two participants. The activity will be given to them and both the participants will fill the sheet for each other.

Read the sentences given below to your colleague, and then encircle the number which closely coincides with the way your partner thinks he/she usually behaves. Before starting, look at the key. Choose one option for each paragraph.

KEY

1 Yes, always
depends

2 Yes, usually

3 Well, it

4 No, not usually

5 No, never

She finds it easy to watch English movies without subtitle.	1 2 3 4 5
She does not speak with stranger.	1 2 3 4 5
She enjoys to talk on her favorite topics.	1 2 3 4 5
She has good memory.	1 2 3 4 5
She has good indicator skills.	1 2 3 4 5

She has a strong decision power.	1 2 3 4 5
She always like to tell her opinion first.	1 2 3 4 5
She listens others carefully even not relevant communication.	1 2 3 4 5
She feels proud to speak in English.	1 2 3 4 5
She makes friends frequently.	1 2 3 4 5
She watches news channels.	1 2 3 4 5
She can tolerate people easily.	1 2 3 4 5
She believes in first impression.	1 2 3 4 5
She is careful about her future.	1 2 3 4 5
She cannot work with other people.	1 2 3 4 5
She is interested in all types of genres to read in free time.	1 2 3 4 5
She is a good entertainer.	1 2 3 4 5

Now, students will introduce their partner to the class that what striking features she has.

Activity 2

Catch your partner

In this activity, everyone in class will stand up and ask the given options to the other fellows. Students are supposed to write one name against each option but without repeating the name again.

Teacher will not try to maintain the discipline in the class rather s/he will free the students to move and access everyone.

Chocolate lover.....

- Watch more than one movie a week.....
- Has been to UK.....
- Love risks
- Has a bird/animal as pet.....
- Is only brother or sister.....
- Know about this game.....
- Gets up early in morning
- Likes chess.....
- Born in March.....
- Believes in spirits
- Can speak Arabic.....
- Goes hiking
- Collection lover.....
- Is wearing something Red
- Eats meat dish.....
- Likes Jonny Depp.....
- Likes working in the different fields

Activity 3

Set your priority

Steps to follow:

Firstly, distribute the sheet among students.

Secondly, ask them to write number as 1, 2, 3 in front of each column in the 'individual ranking' section. They will set their priority on their own and give number as well.

Thirdly, say them to choose a partner and try to convince her that priorities you set are better than her. If she be convinced then she will write your number if not then you will write her number in the section of 'pair ranking'.

Lastly, all the pairs will be asked to repeat step three with another pair and write the numbers in 'group ranking' section.

Following are the qualities of a good leader. Rank them according to the order of priority.

<u>1</u>	QUALITY	INDIVIDUAL RANKING	PAIR RANKING	GROUP RANKING
<u>2</u>	Listen others			
<u>3</u>	Inspire Others			
<u>4</u>	Commitment and Passion			
<u>5</u>	Good Communicator			
<u>6</u>	Decision-Making Capabilities			
<u>7</u>	Accountability			
<u>8</u>	Self-centered			
9	Delegation and Empowerment			
10	Creativity and Innovation			
11	Honesty and Integrity			

Activity 4

Listen your voice on mobile

Follow the steps:

1. Read any language stretch (paragraph/sentences).
2. Record your voice on mobile while reading.
3. Listen your recorded voice carefully.
4. Take notice of your pronunciation (where you are good and which words you did not pronounce accurately).
5. Re-read the passage and try to improve your accent this time.

Activity 5

Word bank

The procedure is:

1. Students must have their diaries or notepads with them for this activity.
2. Any two students from class is supposed to bring one word on daily basis that is new for them.
3. They are responsible to tell the class 'accurate pronunciation' and 'meaning' of the word.
4. Other students will write the word on their diaries or notepads.
5. They will make the sentences on their own related to any situation.
6. They will read their sentences aloud in the class.
7. Teacher will ask the previous words and their usages daily from students. So that, they could memorize the words and they remain fresh in their memory.

Activity 6

Elevator Talk

This activity involves following process:

1. Teacher will divide the class into groups according to the class size.
2. Students will stand in a circle; they will have their backs to each other (this group is inner circle).
3. Students of other group (this is outer circle) will stand in front of the students of inner circle. Now, every student will have a partner of inner circle.
4. Teacher will give 5 to 7 minutes to the students of inner circle to speak on an objective of their life to the students of outer circle.
5. After 7 minutes every student of outer circle will take a clock wise step and now every student of inner circle will have a new partner.

6. Students of outer circle are supposed to repeat the idea of inner circle's student to the next student now they have.

7. This activity will be carried on until every student will listen to each participant who is the part of this activity.

Activity 7

Spot the difference

Follow the phases:

1. Select the images having differences.
2. Paste the images on two different pages.
3. Give names to the pages; it can be 'A or B' / '1 or 2'.
4. Make the groups consisting of two participants.
5. Give one picture to one students and other part of picture to the other member.
6. Now, both the members are supposed to mark the differences and note them without showing their pages to each other.
7. In the end, each group of class will discuss the differences they spotted in the class.

Activity 8

Role play

The activity has following stages:

1. Make the groups of class.
2. Say them to perform any act in front of class. But the topic will not be introduced in the start.
3. Students will select any topic to present. They will make the necessary arrangements on their own as: costumes, props and other accessories.
4. Other students of the class will guess and form the topic according to their own perception.
5. Comment section is mandatory for this activity from students and teacher side.

Activity 9

Your response: if.....

For this activity divide the class into pairs and give them sheet to fill it for each other after asking the given statements.

The answer should be in complete sentences and teacher will just observe the class without interfering them

Statements

1. Everybody who hurt someone turned a statue?
2. You became richest person of your area?
3. Students took class of their teachers once a week?
4. You selected for a movie as heroin?
5. Someone proposed you to whom you like?
6. Someone proposed you to whom you do not like?
7. You had only your favorite people in your life?
8. You got chance to visit PM house?
9. You are not allowed to fulfil your life dream/objective?
10. You had fun all time without having a single work?
11. You were an illiterate person?
12. Someone insults you in front of other people?
13. You got a noble prize for your contribution in research?
14. Your best friend forgot to wish your birthday?
15. You lost your memory?